

A STUDY ON THE BENEFICIARIES' PERCEPTION OF MICRO FINANCE SCHEMES EXTENDED BY THE COMMERCIAL BANKS IN TIRUNELVELI

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Abstract: Microfinance is a dominant instrument to improve poverty and empowerment of rural people and it is efficient in bring communal and financial changes. Nowadays the majority of the Banks have to provide microfinance for the needed public. Micro finance's aim is to improve the standard of living of the rural poor people. It plays a significant role in the self-help group people particularly women empowerment. This paper analyses the perception and beneficiaries of the person having microfinance. An endeavor has been completed in this paper to analyze customers' level of satisfaction towards microfinance schemes in a selected commercial bank in Tirunelveli.

Keywords: micro finance, perception

Introduction

Microfinance is the stipulation of monetary services to low-income customers including clients the self in work, who conventionally be deficient in admission to banking and connected services. Microfinance is a commanding tool to improve deficiency and empowerment of village people and it is efficient in bringing social and monetary changes in rural India with enhanced decision-making ability of village people. Microfinance is a monetary advance that originates in developing countries where it has fruitfully enabled tremendously insolvent people to connect in self, and many cases, to construct wealth and way out of poverty.

Micro Finance

As a result of various winning programs over the world, microfinance has emerged as a gorgeous implement to facilitate the poor, because it not only helps in civilizing livelihood and plummeting their susceptibility but also have a major optimistic contact on women's financial and social empowerment, in terms of their capability to right of entry loans, own creative capital, connects income generate behavior, decision making, and improved mobility.

Statement of the problem

The government is initiation a lot of new program in the country which is appropriate to people's society to bring together the objective of country's growth. As the microfinance services contain started successful and positive impact of women empowerment, now day the banking sectors have to convene the competition among the banking sector. Every year the provision of financial services is attractive the perfect scheme for the needed people.

Objectives of the study

- To estimate, analyze and measure up to the portray the perception and beneficiaries about the assistance of this scheme.
- To value and evaluate the impact by the customers of commercial banks in utilizing in micro finance scheme.
- To offer and suggestions to recover the problems faced by the customers.

Research Methodology

Research design	The research design adopted in the study was a descriptive design
Area of study	The area of the study is in Tirunelveli City
Period of study	The study was conducted for two months
Source of Data	The study is collected both primary and secondary data
Sampling Design	The sampling design is convenient random sampling. The total number of samples is 120.
Tools for analysis	The collected data was analyzed with the help of a percentage table and five points Likert scale

Limitations of the study

The study is limited to the customers' perspective. Therefore it does not coat any performance appraisal or estimation on e-banking services from bankers' viewpoint.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1.1

Demographic profile of the respondents

S. No.	Particulars	Classification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	78	65
		Female	42	35
2.	Age	Below 25 years	18	15
		Above 26 - 35	46	38.33
		Above 36 - 45	38	31.67
		More than 45 years	18	15
3.	Educational Qualification	School level	10	8.33
		ITI / Diploma	18	15
		Graduate	40	33.33
		Post Graduate	28	23.33
		Professional	24	20
4.	Monthly Income	Below Rs. 10,000	10	8.33
		Rs. 10,001 – 15,000	28	23.33
		Rs. 15,001 – 20,000	38	31.67
		Rs. 20001 – 25,000	19	15.83
		Above 25,000	25	20.83
5.	Average monthly transaction	Below Rs. 10,000	27	22.50
		Rs. 10,001 – 15,000	22	18.33
		Rs. 15,001 – 20,000	35	29.17
		Rs. 20,001 – 25,000	26	21.67
		Above Rs. 25000	10	8.33

Interpretation

From the above table, it is indicated that 65 % of the respondents are male and 35 % of the respondents are female. Out of the total respondents, 15 % of the respondents are 25 years old and below. 38.33 % of the respondents' age between 26 -35, 31.67 % of the respondents belong to the age group between 36 – 45, and 15 % of the respondents are above 45 years of

age. Out of the total respondents, 31.33 and 23.33 % of the respondents are graduates and postgraduates correspondingly. 23.33 % of the respondents are in the income level between Rs. 10001 -15,000. In this group 20.83 % of the respondents' income level is above Rs. 25,000. 29.17 % of the respondents spend Rs 15,001 – 20,000 of their monthly e-banking transactions Only 8.33 of the respondents spend more than Rs. 25,000 for their e-banking transactions.

Perception of the sufficiency of Loan

The subsequent table presents the perception of the beneficiary relating to the sufficiency of loan

Table 1.2

Sufficiency of Loan

Sufficiency	Male	Female	Total
Sufficient	36	32	68 (56.67%)
Not Sufficient	30	22	52 (43.33)
Total	66	54	120 (100 %)

Source : Primary data

The above table shows that 52 constituting (43.33 percent) comprising 30 male and 22 female of the sample respondents felt that the loan amount is not sufficient while 68 respondents representing (56.67 percent) comprising 36 male and 32 female respondents, of the sample opined that the loan amount given is sufficient. Most of the beneficiaries are satisfied with a sufficient part of the micro-credit loan given by the banks.

Opinion of the benefits derived

The following table represents the opinion of the beneficiaries on the payback derivative from the microfinance schemes.

Table 1.3**Customer opinion regarding the micro credit scheme**

Opinion	Male	Female	Total
Benefited	38	34	72 (60 %)
Not Benefited	28	20	48 (40 %)
Total	66	54	120 (100 %)

Source: Primary data

Table 1.3 reveals that 72 respondents (60 percent) of the beneficiaries have benefited after borrowing the loan under the micro-credit scheme and remain 48 respondents (40 percent) feel that they were not benefited. It depends on the monetary use of the funds raised by them the banks.

Table 1.4**Customer suggestion regarding effectiveness of micro credit schemes**

Sl No.	Factors	Respondent's Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	No idea	DA	SDA	Weighted score	Total Score	Percentile Points
1.	New scheme for differently abled persons	28	36	13	20	23	386	600	64.33
2.	Interest subsidy should be given	35	27	25	18	15	409	600	68.17
3.	Loan amount should be raised	28	40	12	21	19	297	600	49.5
4.	Immediate facilitate for problems or query	28	38	18	17	19	399	600	66.5
5.	Secure in providing individual information	32	38	18	20	12	418	600	69.67
6.	Safe with online transaction	40	35	15	20	10	435	600	72.5
7	Uniform services	26	32	28	18	16	394	600	65.67

As per the above calculation, a total of 72.5 percentile is a better overall process of safe with an online transaction. Secure in providing individual information is also fine with 69.67 percentile points, followed by interest subsidiary given

Suggestions

- Banks should make their internet banking services client-friendly with simple process systems.
- Increasing more number of credit schemes
- Customers should be made educated about the use of all the products and services of banks.

Conclusion

Microfinance institutions now recommend essential financial services like insurance savings, and loans to poor people and are less providential. As the Microfinance Schemes bring a large number of benefits to the poor, the government should take compulsory steps to expand these schemes and create them popular among the poor.

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